

biodiversity

SUCCESS STORIES

No. 2 March 2014

Edited by
BioGenRes - Italian Network of Genetic Resources
www.biogenres.it

Biodiversity: a gross value for a *great beauty*

In recent years a rising common concern is looking at biodiversity concept with a new sight, attempting to evaluate its economical value, as ground step for supporting measures proposed by national governments and international committees. Although this utilitarian view applied to a complex concept could cause an underestimation of the true potential of biological resources, nowadays a wide spectrum of direct and indirect quantifiable values has been recognized as tightly correlated to biodiversity.

These economic criteria have been simplistically split into two distinct categories, each of them attempting to reconstitute a concrete outline of biodiversity preservation as a profitable entity. Within this distinction benefits straightly arising from natural resources exploitation are defined as direct-use values, and include consumptive and productive use of biological species. Many examples come easy to mind. Harvesting and direct consumption of plants is a source of food, as well as of active principles extracted for traditional medicine and pharmaceutical purposes. Fish is a relevant source of proteins, widely exploited through fishery and aquaculture. Fuel is a hugely-exploited product of biodiversity, in form of forestry firewood, natural biogas, or fossils sources like coal and petroleum. In addition, productive values are derivatives of the consumptive values, as they come from primary sources and pass through industrial process, thus increasing their economical value and marketing potential. Examples are given by wool, silk, timber, paper, gum, likewise products banned from trading or commonly perceived as "prohibited" like furs, ivory trunks or coral jewels.

The economic "taste" of direct-use values is easily perceived and continuously growing thanks to the relevant contribution of biotechnologies, that are re-modeling and increasing the mere value of genetic resources. Conversely, it seems often more difficult to quantify and conceive the true incidence of the commonly named indirect or non-use values, apparently lacking in a direct and countable benefit. Nevertheless there is a recognized value provided by the so-called ecosystem services, that are the active mechanisms through which human activities are sustained by natural ecosystems and all the living things they host. The assumption that these natural processes can be thought as a concrete service is consistent with the "industrial" profile held by, for instance, conversion of sunlight to energy through photosynthetic carbon dioxide fixation; retention of nutrients ratio carried

out by carbon, oxygen, nitrogen, sulphur and phosphorus cycles; climate regulation, moisture control and recharge of ground stream through water cycle; recycling of organic waste through biodegradation or moderation of flood damage; control of erosion through soil formation and its interaction with plant root system.

Undoubtedly the better functioning of these ecoservices is strictly related to the preservation of high biodiversity rates. Exactly in the same way as a company employing several and distinct competences will have an higher impact on the market. Nonetheless it results difficult to re-think the value of a natural complex like Amazon forest, given that our mind is instinctively used to consider these entity as a priceless

heritage. A way to estimate this value exists, and is related to the cost we should effort to replace ecosystem action with human-made surrogates. This forecast has been attempted and led to enormous numbers, in the measure of approximately twice the world gross national product. Facing this awareness we have the true perception of how big damage could represent for global economy the past, present and future loss of biodiversity. Every time we create a tear in the ecosystem fabric, we need to pay for it, more and more, to provide again the lost service. In some way, indirect values acquire a fundamental importance, that is even more incident on planet balance than the more easily perceived value of direct exploitation.

Without forgetting that a rational use of the priceless treasure represented by biological resources, should consider within non-use values, also the social and aesthetic impact of nature on people. Natural landscape, national parks or zoological and botanical gardens, in fact providing several opportunities for recreational activities (e.g. bird watching, diving, eco-tourism, hiking, game fishing, photography, etc), constitute a great attractive for millions of people and therefore represent a significant and growing income for state economy. People are concerned with biodiversity more than governments expect, and there is even an ethical issue, well perceived in many cultures, that is our responsibility to future generations to protect from extinction what Nature gave to us. This final consideration seems irrational to conclude an economical dissertation, but it is also true that the "religious" sense for biodiversity constitutes a surplus value to not underestimate in many contexts. Not only in India where plants and animals like peepal tree, lotus, cow, monkey, peacock or snake are still worshipped as sacred, but even in Western countries, where the belief that nature is God's creation is still cited as a fundamental reason to protect biodiversity.

Given these considerations, we should not forget that when, in 1992 the Convention on Biological Diversity established in Rio de Janeiro recognized biodiversity as a "common concern of humankind", was indirectly affirming that it has an economical value. Unfortunately, more than twenty years later, this value is still culpably unknown and underestimated.

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